

BIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF WATER QUALITY AND BIODIVERSITY IN LAKE PARCHES, TULCEA COUNTY

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Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the biological quality of the water and the biodiversity of Lake Parches in the pre-delta area, Tulcea County, using phytoplankton as indicator organisms. The phytoplankton samples were collected at the end of September 2021.

Species composition plays a key role in the functioning of ecosystems. Diversity is a functional and structural parameter of ecosystems, a descriptor of their health. Phytoplankton Alpha diversity was calculated using the Shannon (H'), Gini-Simpson Index (HS), Brillouin index (HB), Berger-Parker dominance Index (d), and the Evenness Index (J') (the natural logarithm was used for calculations). Results obtained in all four stations suggest that the phytoplankton diversity in the Parches Lake aquatic ecosystem is good.

The saprobiological analysis is based on the results - the assessment criteria delivered by the classic "saprobe system" (1977). Based on the list of indicators, the saprobic index is calculated according to the Pantle Bulk method. The values obtained after calculating the SI index (Saprobity index Pantle and Bulk) suggested that the water fell into the second class of quality.

Introduction

The term phytoplankton includes all photoautotrophic aquatic microorganisms (plants that feed through photosynthesis). Phytoplankton is a polyphyletic group with great variability in size, shape, colour, type of metabolism, and life traits [1]. Phytoplankton is one of the most important components of natural aquatic systems, being the primary producer [2]. Phytoplankton has been revealed as a useful tool for the estimation of impacts on the aquatic ecosystem due to its rapid response to changes in environmental conditions, thus allowing a rapid assessment of water quality [3], [4]. The presence of certain phytoplankton taxonomic groups can be used as indicators of water quality [5].

The term biodiversity can be defined in many ways, usually referring to the variety of life forms at all levels of organization in an ecosystem. Biodiversity can be defined as specific taxonomic diversity, functional diversity, genetic diversity, phylogenetic diversity, or chemical diversity [6].

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Biodiversity includes not only rare, endangered, and endangered species but also lesser-known species such as microorganisms, molds, and invertebrates [7].

Diversity is a central concept to ecology, and its measurement is central to any study of ecosystem health. Diversity is a functional and structural parameter of ecosystems and a descriptor for their state of health.

A better understanding of the relationship between variability in phytoplankton diversity and its effects on ecosystem processes is needed.

Materials and Methods

Study area

The Somova-Parches aquatic complex is a pre-delta area of the Danube Delta.

The total area of the Somova-Parches aquatic complex is 9170 ha, of which 2025 ha are covered by water (Török, 2006).

The lake complex has in its composition: Gorgonel lake (141 ha), Rotundu lake (228 ha), Telincea (188 ha), Parches Lake (196 ha), Morun lake, Somova backwater (123 ha), Casla lake (153 ha), Somova lake (149 ha) and Ciorciovata lake, Babele lake, lacul Petica lake, Gasca lake (Burada et al., 2016) (figure 1).

Figure 1. Somova–Parches aquatic complex map , source Google Earth

Plankton Sampling

In the autumn season, September 2021, from the superficial water horizon, biological samples were collected to determine the abundance of phytoplankton and draw up the fauna list of species, methods described by Florea Luiza (2007). Phytoplankton samples were preserved with Lugol's solution and kept in the dark until analysis. The samples were taken from 4 stations established with the help of a GPS navigation system (Table 1).

Table 1. GPS coordinates correspond to the related stations

Station	Latitude	Longitude
P1	45°13'32.88"N	28°34'58.95"E
P2	45°13'53.45"N	28°35'2.79"E
P3	45°13'21.59"N	28°35'49.81"E
P4	45°13'33.16"N	28°35'26.37"E

Data Analyses

Diversity indices

Phytoplankton Alpha diversity was calculated using the Shannon Index (H'), Gini-Simpson Index (GS), Brillouin index (HB), Berger-Parker dominance Index (d), and the Evenness Index or Pielou index (J').

The Shannon index (H'), also known as the Shannon-Wiener or Shannon-Weaver index, is one of the most widely used indicators of biological diversity. It derives from information theory [7] and expresses the diversity of a community by combining two essential components: specific richness (the number of species) and evenness (the relative proportion of individuals of each species).

The Simpson index (D) takes into account not only the total number of classes, but also the weight of each class it being expressed in three forms (D, 1-D, and 1/D).

The Brillouin index (HB) is a measure of diversity used in ecology to assess the diversity of a community when a complete inventory of it has been made or when the sample is not a random sample of a larger community.

The Berger-Parker index (d) illustrates this perfectly, providing a straightforward way to analyze species' dominance within ecological communities. By applying this index, essential patterns in ecosystem functioning can be identified.

The Evenness or Pielou index (J') is a standardized version of the Shannon index, highlighting the ratios between class frequencies [8].

Saprobic index (S)

To determine the water quality class, they use algal species in our country, and the Pantle-Buck method (1955) is used. The calculation formula for the saprobic index is:

$S = \frac{\sum(s \cdot h_i)}{\sum(h_i)}$, where:

s- Numerical value belonging to the saprob area according to Order 161/2006

h- Numerical abundance of individuals of a particular taxon

Results and Discussions

Taxonomic

Microscopic analyses of phytoplankton samples revealed several 58 taxa, which can be taxonomically classified into 4 groups (Bacillariaceae, Chlorophyceae, Euglenophyceae, and Cyanophyceae). More than half belong to Bacillariaceae (52-69%), followed by Chlorophyceae with 14-28%, and followed by Euglenophyceae (9-14%) and Cyanophyceae with 0-10%.

In station 1 (P1), the dominant species in the Bacillariophyceae group is *Cymatopleura solea* (figure 2), in the Euglenophyceae group is *Trachelomonas planctonica* (figure 3), and in the Chlorophyceae group is *Scenedesmus quadricauda* (figure 4).

In station 2 (P2), the dominant species in the Bacillariophyceae group is *Cocconeis placentula* (figure 2), in the Euglenophyceae group is *Trachelomonas verrucosa* (figure 3), and in the Chlorophyceae group is *Scenedesmus quadricauda* (figure 4). Equally, in the Cyanophyceae group, species from the genus *Phormidium* predominate (Figure 5).

In station 3 (P3), the dominant species in the Bacillariophyceae group is *Pinularia viridis* (figure 2), in the Euglenophyceae group is *Trachelomonas verrucosa* (figure 3), and in the Chlorophyceae group is *Scenedesmus quadricauda* (figure 4).

In the fourth station (P4), the dominant species in the Bacillariophyceae group is *Synedra berolinensis* (figure 2), in the Euglenophyceae group is *Trachelomonas planctonica* (figure 3), in the Chlorophyceae group, the species *Scenedesmus quadricauda* predominates (figure 4) and in the Cyanophyceae group, the species *Aphanotece stagnina* and *Phormidium faveolarum* predominate in the same proportion (Figure 5).

Figure 2. Dominant species in the Bacillariophyceae group

Figure 3. Dominant species in the Euglenophyceae group

Figure 4. Dominant species in the Chlorophyceae group

Figure 5. Dominant species in the Cyanophyceae group

Diversity indices

The Shannon diversity index (H) is derived from information theory and represents the uncertainty with which we can predict to which a randomly selected individual from a community will belong. If a community contains only one species, then the uncertainty is zero, because we can be sure that a randomly selected individual belongs to that species, and if a community contains several species, the greater the uncertainty. The values of this index are usually between 1.5 and 3.5, showing a more balanced estimate of diversity. From the point of view of the H index, we can say that the diversity in the Parches Lake aquatic ecosystem is good; the value of this index fell between 2.58 and 3.157 (Table 2). High values of the Shannon index reflect high species diversity and a uniform distribution of individuals among species.

The Simpson index (D or GS) considers both richness and evenness, the latter having a greater influence than species richness. The probability that two randomly selected individuals belong to the same species decreases as the species richness of the community increases, so the Simpson index also decreases as species richness increases, which is not very intuitive. The Gini-Simpson index is simply the 1-Simpson index and increases as community species richness increases [5]. The values of this index are usually between 0 and 1; values close to 1 show a high diversity, and values close to 0 show a low diversity. From the point of view of the GS index, we can say that the diversity in the Parches Lake aquatic ecosystem is good, with the values of this index approaching 1 (0.886-0.943).

Overall, the Brillouin index (HB) values tend to be close to those of the Shannon index, but are consistently lower [9]. From a mathematical perspective, the index has a higher sensitivity compared to the Shannon index, which justifies its frequent use and recommendation in specialized research.

The Berger-Parker index (d) has values between 0 and 1; according to this index, low dominance between 0.1-0.2 often indicates high diversity. In the analyzed ecosystem, the Berger-Parker index recorded values between 0.125-0.226, thus resulting in a low dominance, which suggests a healthy algal ecosystem (Table 2).

The index value ranges from 0 to 1, where a value close to 1 indicates a uniform distribution of individuals among species, while lower values suggest a pronounced dominance of one or a few species. Therefore, the Pielou index provides a complementary perspective to diversity indices, contributing to the understanding of the degree of balance and homogeneity

of an ecological community [6]. However, Pielou Evenness is higher in stations P3 and P4, which indicates that there is a more uniform distribution of species within the phytoplankton community in these stations.

The comparative analysis of alpha diversity (Figure 6) shows us the same trend, in the sense that the best diversity is found in station P1 and the lowest in station P2.

Table 2. Alpha diversity indices

Station \ Indices	P1	P2	P3	P4
H	3.157	2.58	3.03	2.863
GS	0.943	0.886	0.937	0.919
HB	3.027	2.343	2.849	2.734
d	0.125	0.226	0.113	0.181
J'	0.74	0.78	0.86	0.85

Figure 6. The comparative analysis of alpha diversity

Saprobic index (S)

The organisms adapted to live in contaminated waters are saprobic organisms; therefore, the degree of water pollution can be calculated based on their presence and quantity. The saprobic system divides aquatic organisms into the following saprobic groups: polysaprobic organisms, mesosaprobic organisms (alfamesosaprobic and betamesosaprobic), and oligosaprobic organisms [10]. (Figure 3). As can be seen in Figure 4, in all stations (P1, P2, P3, and P4), the species from the area of mesosaprobies β predominate. The organisms in the β -2.0 category recorded the highest abundance (71.55-77.02%), as can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7. The numerical abundance of individuals in each saprobe category, 2021

According to order 161/2006 [11], for values of the Saprob index between 1.00 and 1.80, the water falls into the first quality class with an absent impurity and an ultra-oligotrophic trophic level, and if the index takes values between 1.80 and 2.30, the water has the second quality, it has a moderate impurity and an oligotrophic trophic level. When the index takes values between 2.3 and 2.7, the water is in the III class of quality with a moderate to critical impurity and a mesotrophic trophic level, and for its values between 2.7 and 3.2 the water is in the IV class of quality with a strong impurity and a eutrophic trophic level, and for values higher than 3.2 the water falls into the Vth class of quality with a strong to very strong impurity and a hypertrophic trophic level. Table 3 shows the values of the Saprobe Index at the stations obtained in the Parches Lake aquatic ecosystem. Analysing these values (1.941–2.022), the water of this aquatic ecosystem fell into the II class of quality.

Table 3. Quality class in Parches Lake, 2021

Sampling stations	P1	P2	P3	P4
Saprobic Index (S)	2.022	1.941	1.970	2.001
Quality class	II	II	II	II
Impurity	Moderate impurity	Moderate impurity	Moderate impurity	Moderate impurity
Trophic level	Oligotrophic	Oligotrophic	Oligotrophic	Oligotrophic
Ecological status	Good	Good	Good	Good

Conclusions

This study was developed to create an overview of the algal composition and the state of health of the aquatic ecosystem, Lake Parches.

In terms of relative abundance, diatoms dominated in phytoplankton samples at all sampling stations. The structure of algal communities is typical in the autumn season for oligotrophic lakes with low mineralization, which are not affected by high anthropogenic pressure. In the algal communities analyzed, mesosaprobic organisms predominate, the water shows a moderate pollution, and was classified in the II class of quality.

We can conclude that both the diversity of the phytoplankton and the ecological status of the aquatic ecosystem of Lake Parches, in all 4 stations, is good according to the specialized literature, the water falling into the II class of quality. Freshwater ecosystems with good biodiversity, healthy and unpolluted, produce fewer greenhouse gases and provide food.

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